

R Script industrial DoE

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Used Libraries:

I use the following libraries to generate the output:

```
library(OptimalDesign)
```

```
## Warning: Paket 'OptimalDesign' wurde unter R Version 4.1.3 erstellt
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
## Warning in register(): Can't find generic `scale_type` in package ggplot2 to  
## register S3 method.
```

```
library(ggpubr)
```

Generate an industrial used Design of Experiment

I use an cubic design, as these are used in Life Sciences. I assume an quadratic model with a linear interaction and an influence of the linear factors itself.

The first factor (x_1) lies in a range between inclusive 0 and 170 inclusive.

The second factor (x_2) lies in a range between inclusive 10 and 240 inclusive.

I assume that one wants to conduct an experiment on 51 plots. The user can freely choose the needed number of plots.

There are no replicates nor repetitions.

```
Fx <-  
Fx_cube(  
  formula=~ x1 + x2 + I(x1 ^ 2) + I(x2 ^ 2) + I(x1 * x2),  
  n.levels = c(51, 51),  
  lower = c(0, 10),  
  upper = c(170, 240)  
)
```

```
## [1] Call of the function:  
## Fx_cube(formula = ~x1 + x2 + I(x1^2) + I(x2^2) + I(x1 * x2),  
##       lower = c(0, 10), upper = c(170, 240), n.levels = c(51, 51))
```

```
# The D-optimal design of size 51 without replications  
design <- od_KL(Fx, 51, bin = TRUE, t.max = 25)
```

```
## [1] Call of the function:
## od_KL(Fx = Fx, N = 51, bin = TRUE, t.max = 25)
## [1] Call of the function:
## od_REX(Fx = Fx, crit = "D", track = FALSE)
## [1] Running od_D_KL_bin for cca 25 seconds starting at 2022-04-26 15:53:08.
## [1] The problem size is n=2601, m=6, N=51
## [1] Setting K=10, L=51
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 0 Value: 3056144.332081 Efficiency: 0.604124
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 1 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 2 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 3 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 4 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 5 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 6 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 7 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 8 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 9 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 10 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 11 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 12 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 13 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 14 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 15 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 16 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 17 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 18 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 19 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 20 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 21 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 22 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 23 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin Time: 24.1 Value: 4752895.705487 Efficiency: 0.939529
## [1] od_D_KL_bin finished after 25.02 seconds at 2022-04-26 15:53:33
## [1] with 196 restarts and 9364 exchanges.
```

```
od_plot(Fx, design$w.best, Fx[, 2:3], return.pool = FALSE)
```

```
## [1] Call of the function:
## od_plot(Fx = Fx, w = design$w.best, X = Fx[, 2:3], return.pools = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in dirder(Fx, w, crit = crit, h = h, echo = FALSE): The information
## matrix is badly conditioned and there may be problems computing the directional
## derivative.
```



```
## $call
## od_plot(Fx = Fx, w = design$w.best, X = Fx[, 2:3], return.pools = FALSE)
##
## $Pools
## [1] "Pool return suppressed."
```

We can use a structure, that is used in 'agricolaeplotr' package to plot the design in a known way.

The prototype requires to use a list, where the fieldbook is named \(\book\).

```
d <- list()
d$book <- Fx[design$supp, c(1:3)]
d$book <- as.data.frame(d$book)
```

We can use a function to have more control, compared to the published ones in \(\agricolaeplotr\).

```
plot_designs_full_control <-
  function(design,
           ncols,
           nrows,
           y = "row",
           x = "col",
           factor_name = "x1",
           labels = "plots",
           width = 1,
           height = 1,
           space_width = 0.95,
           shift_x = 0,
```

```

    shift_y = 0,
    space_height = 0.85,
    reverse_y = FALSE,
    reverse_x = FALSE)
{
  design$book$plots <- 1:length(design$book[, 1])
  plots <- 1:length(design$book[, 1])
  if (ncols * nrows >= length(plots)) {
    nas <- rep(NaN, ncols * nrows - length(plots))
    plots <- c(plots, nas)
    mat <- matrix(plots, byrow = TRUE, ncol = ncols)
    dims <- dim(mat)
    table <- as.table(mat)
    rownames(table) <- 1:dims[1]
    colnames(table) <- 1:dims[2]
    table <- as.data.frame(table)
    colnames(table) <- c("row", "col", "plots")
    table$row <- as.numeric(table$row)
    table$col <- as.numeric(table$col)
    table <- merge(table, design$book, by.x = "plots",
                  by.y = "plots")
    table$row <- as.numeric(table$row) * height
    table$col <- as.numeric(table$col) * width
    if (reverse_y == TRUE) {
      table$row <- abs(table$row - max(table$row)) +
        min(table$row)
    }
    if (reverse_x == TRUE) {
      table$col <- abs(table$col - max(table$col)) +
        min(table$col)
    }

    table$col <- table$col + shift_x
    table$row <- table$row + shift_y

    plt <- ggplot(table, aes_string(x, y)) +
      geom_tile(
        aes_string(fill = factor_name),
        width = width *
          space_width,
        height = height * space_height
      ) +
      theme_bw() + theme(line = element_blank()) +
      geom_text(aes_string(label = labels), colour = "black")
    plt
    return(plt)
  }
  else {
    stop(
      paste(
        "You have in multiplication of ncols:",
        ncols,
        "and nrows:",
        nrows,
        "Elements."
      )
    )
  }
}

```

```

    "You need at minimum a product of both higher than",
    length(plots)
  )
)
}
}

p1 <-
plot_designs_full_control(
  d,
  7,
  8,
  factor_name = "x1",
  shift_x = -0.5,
  shift_y = -0.5,
  space_width = 1,
  space_height = 1,
  labels = "x1",
  reverse_y = TRUE
) + scale_fill_viridis_c()
p1

```



```

q1 <-
plot_designs_full_control(
  d,
  7,
  8,
  factor_name = "x2",

```

```

shift_x = -0.5,
shift_y = -0.5,
space_width = 1,
space_height = 1,
labels = "x2",
reverse_y = TRUE
) + scale_fill_viridis_c()
q1

```



```

ggarrange(p1,
  q1,
  labels = LETTERS[1:2],
  ncol = 1,
  nrow = 2)

```


Randomization of a factor

For those wishing a random order of all plots:

```
# will be an optional:
set.seed(2871623)
d$book <- d$book[sample(1:nrow(d$book)), ]

p1 <-
  plot_designs_full_control(
    d,
    7,
    8,
    factor_name = "x1",
    shift_x = -0.5,
    shift_y = -0.5,
    space_width = 1,
    space_height = 1,
    labels = "x1",
    reverse_y = TRUE
  ) + scale_fill_viridis_c()

q1 <-
  plot_designs_full_control(
    d,
    7,
    8,
```

```

factor_name = "x2",
shift_x = -0.5,
shift_y = -0.5,
space_width = 1,
space_height = 1,
labels = "x2",
reverse_y = TRUE
) + scale_fill_viridis_c()

ggarrange(p1,
  q1,
  labels = LETTERS[1:2],
  ncol = 1,
  nrow = 2)

```


Session Information

```
sessionInfo()
```

```

## R version 4.1.2 (2021-11-01)
## Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64 (64-bit)
## Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19044)
##
## Matrix products: default
##
## locale:

```

```

## [1] LC_COLLATE=German_Germany.1252 LC_CTYPE=German_Germany.1252
## [3] LC_MONETARY=German_Germany.1252 LC_NUMERIC=C
## [5] LC_TIME=German_Germany.1252
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] ggpubr_0.4.0      ggplot2_3.3.5      OptimalDesign_1.0.1
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] tidyselect_1.1.1  xfun_0.29          bslib_0.3.1       purrr_0.3.4
## [5] carData_3.0-5     colorspace_2.0-2   vctrs_0.3.8       generics_0.1.1
## [9] viridisLite_0.4.0 htmltools_0.5.2    yaml_2.2.1        utf8_1.2.2
## [13] rlang_1.0.2       jquerylib_0.1.4    pillar_1.6.5      glue_1.6.0
## [17] withr_2.4.3       DBI_1.1.2          matrixStats_0.61.0 lifecycle_1.0.1
## [21] plyr_1.8.6        stringr_1.4.0      munsell_0.5.0     ggsignif_0.6.3
## [25] gtable_0.3.0      evaluate_0.14      labeling_0.4.2    knitr_1.37
## [29] fastmap_1.1.0     fansi_0.5.0        highr_0.9         Rcpp_1.0.8
## [33] broom_0.7.11      scales_1.1.1       backports_1.4.1   jsonlite_1.7.2
## [37] abind_1.4-5       farver_2.1.0       digest_0.6.29     stringi_1.7.6
## [41] rstatix_0.7.0     dplyr_1.0.7        cowplot_1.1.1     grid_4.1.2
## [45] cli_3.1.0         tools_4.1.2        magrittr_2.0.1    sass_0.4.0
## [49] tibble_3.1.6      crayon_1.4.2       tidyr_1.1.4       car_3.0-12
## [53] pkgconfig_2.0.3   ellipsis_0.3.2     assertthat_0.2.1  rmarkdown_2.11
## [57] rstudioapi_0.13  R6_2.5.1           compiler_4.1.2

```